

Spectrophotometric Studies on the Complexes of Eriochrome Black-T with Titanium (III & IV)

S. M. S. Akhtar, Naseer Ahmad, and S. M. F. Rahman

Eriochrome Black-T (H_2L) exists in three differently coloured species in solution¹ and the equilibria between the three species are:

Eriochrome Black-T produces a green-coloured complex with titanium(III) in aqueous and with titanium (IV) in ethanolic media.

Procedure.—Titanium (III) chloride solution was prepared from $TiCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ crystals and standardised. Titanium (IV) chloride ($TiCl_4$, 12% w/v soln. containing 15% HCl, B.D.H.) was used for preparing its solution and standardised. $0.2 \times 10^{-3}M$ of Eriochrome Black-T was prepared in air-free double distilled water or in 98% ethanol.

The wave-length maxima were ascertained for the dye and the mixtures of the dye and the metal salts according to Vosburgh and Cooper's method². It was found to be 525 $m\mu$ for the dye and for its titanium (III) complex in aqueous medium; the λ_{max} was 525 $m\mu$ at pH 3.0 to 6.4, 565 $m\mu$ at pH 7.1 to 10.1, and 550 $m\mu$ at pH 11.5. The absorption maximum for titanium (IV) complex in ethanolic medium lies at 530 $m\mu$ and 600 $m\mu$.

The composition of the titanium(III) dye complex (using $0.1 \times 10^{-3}M$ aqueous solutions) was 1:3 (metal: ligand) by Job's method of continued variations³ and also by the mole-ratio and slope-ratio methods⁴.

The interaction of titanium(III) chloride and the dye was studied in buffer solutions of pH 4.2, 7.2, 9.0, and 12.0 and the ratios of 1:3, 1:2, 1:2, and 1:1 titanium: dye, respectively, were found out, showing other complexes also, which can be represented by the following empirical formulas:

1. Martell and Calvin, "Chemistry of Metal Chelate Compounds", 1959, p. 486, Prentice Hall, Inc., N.Y.
2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.
3. *Compt. rend.*, 1925, **180**, 928.
4. Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.

To $0.2 \times 10^{-2} M$ solution (300 ml) of Eriochrome Black-T was added dropwise titanium(III) chloride ($0.2 \times 10^{-2} M$, 200 ml), when a reddish brown flocculent precipitate appeared. It was washed with water and dried in a vacuum desiccator (H_2SO_4). The dried product was brownish green in colour. The complex was found to be free of chloride.

It was fused with fusion mixture in a platinum crucible. The fused mass was dissolved in HCl (dil.) and titanium was determined as hydroxide and sulphur, as barium sulphate.

The results indicated a ratio of 2:3 (metal: dye) and the interaction therefore can be represented by the equation:

The titanium (IV) complex with the dye was studied by the three methods, stated above, in ethanolic media at 530 $m\mu$ and 600 $m\mu$ and the ratio found was 1:2 (metal: dye).

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
ALIGARH MUSLIM UNIVERSITY,
ALIGARH.

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